

TASVIRLAR ASOSIDA HAVO IFLOSLANISH DARAJASINI BAHOLASH

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***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu tadqiqot ishida sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida havo ifloslanish darajasini baholash masalasi o‘rganilib, uni yechish uchun neyron tarmoq modeli taklif etildi. Taklif etilgan model havodagi zarrachalarni aks ettiruvchi tasvirlardan foydalanilib, havodagi PM 2.5 zarrachalar miqdorini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Bunda CNN yordamida dastlab tasvirdan belgilar ajratib olindi, so‘ngra FNN orqali regressiya muammosi sifatida o‘rganildi. Natijada model asosida tasvirdagi havoni vizual holatiga ko‘ra PM 2.5 qiymatini bashoratlash amalga oshirildi.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Havo, PM 2.5, ifloslanish, tasvir, belgi, model, neyron tarmoq, EfficientNetV2B0, Deep Learning.*

Kirish

Atmosferani ifloslanish darajasini ortishi inson salomatligi, ekologiya va iqlim o‘zgarishiga bevosita jiddiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatmoqda. Bu umumjamiyat global muammosi bo‘lib, uni barataraf etish dolzarb vazifaga aylandi. Ayniqsa, diametri 2.5 mikrondan kichik bo‘lgan zarrachalar (PM 2.5) inson nafas yo‘llariga chuqur kirib, surunkali kasalliklarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. An‘anaviy usullar hamda maxsus stansiyalar va sensorga asoslangan o‘lchov tizimlari yuqori aniqlikka ega bo‘lsada, ularni qamrovi tor va texnik xizmat xarajatlari yuqoridir [1].

So‘nggi yillarda sun’iy intellekt va chuqur o‘rganish (Deep Learning) usullari asosida havo sifatini tasvirlar yordamida baholash yo‘nalishi jadal rivojlanmoqda. Bu yondashuv an‘anaviy sensor va monitoring tizimlariga nisbatan arzon, keng qamrovli va tezkor ma‘lumot olish imkonini beradi. Sputnik, dron va shahar videokuzatuv kameralaridan yordamida olingan tasvirlar sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida tahlil qilinib, atmosferadagi ifloslanish darajasi, gaz konsentratsiyasi hamda zarrachalar tarqalishi aniqlash imkonini beradi. Mazkur yondashuv nafaqat real vaqt rejimi monitoringni ta‘minlaydi, balki havo sifatini bashoratlashda ham samarali hisoblanadi [2]. Chunki tasvirlar orqali havodagi chang, tuman, yorug‘lik diffuziyasi va atmosfera tarqalish effektlari aniqlash mumkin bo‘lib, ular PM 2.5 konsentratsiyasi bilan bevosita bog‘liqdir [3]. Mazkur ishda tasvirlar asosida havodagi PM 2.5 darajasini bashoratlash uchun regressiya modeli ishlab chiqilgan.

Ayni paytda havo sifatini aniqlash bo‘yicha ko‘plab ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Dastlabki ishlar esa asosan fizik sensorlar va meteorologik o‘lchov stansiyalaridan olingan ma‘lumotlarga tayangan [4, 5]. Masalan, AQShning EPA va Xitoyning CAMS tizimlari real vaqtda PM 2.5 konsentratsiyasini o‘lchash uchun keng ko‘lamli sensorga asoslangan tarmoqlarni tashkil etadi [6]. Biroq, bu kabi usullar infratuzilma va texnik xizmat ko‘rsatish xarajatlari yuqori bo‘lganligi uchun ularni global miqyosda qo‘llashni imkoni yo‘q.

So‘nggi yillarda masofaviy zondlash (Remote Sensing) texnologiyalari jadal rivojlandi va sun’iy yo‘ldosh tasvirlari orqali havodagi zarrachalar miqdorini baholash imkoniyati paydo bo‘ldi [7]. Xususan, NASAning MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) va Sentinel-2 sputniklari orqali olingan ma’lumotlar asosida PM2.5 konsentratsiyasini baholashda ayerosol optik zichlik (Aerosol Optical Depth, AOD) ko‘rsatkichidan foydalanilgan. Olingan ma’lumotlarga regressiya usullariga asoslangan modellar yordamida ishlov berilib, atmosferadagi mayda zarrachalar tarqalishini aniqlash va ularni inson salomatligiga ta’sirini baholash amalga oshirilgan. Bu kabi modellar optik zichlik va PM2.5 darajasi orasidagi bog‘lanish asosida havo sifatini fazoviy-vaqt taqsimotini aniqlashda yuqori samara ko‘rsatgan [8]. Landsat 8 sputnik tasvirlari asosida esa spektral indekslar, ya’ni NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), NDBI (Normalized Difference Built-up Index) va MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index) qo‘llanilib, havodagi o‘zgarishlar kuzatilgan va talqin etish bo‘yicha tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilgan. Ushbu indekslar orqali o‘simlik qoplami, shahar infratuzilmasi va suv manbalari dinamikasini aniqlash hamda ularni PM2.5 va AOD kabi ifloslanish ko‘rsatkichlari bilan bog‘liqligi o‘rganilgan [9]. Biroq, yuqorida keltirib o‘tilgan yondashuvlarda faqat fizik parametrlardan foydalanilganligi uchun havo vizual belgilarini bevosita tahlil qilish imkoniyati mavjud emas. Shuning uchun so‘nggi tadqiqotlarda tasvirlarga asoslangan sun’iy intellekt yondashuvlari keng qo‘llanilmoqda [10]. Xususan, Zhang va boshq. (2020) tasvirlardan PM 2.5 ni bashoratlash uchun ResNet50 modelini qo‘llab, 0.85 aniqlikka erishgan [11]. Li va boshq. (2022) esa DenseNet arxitekturasidan foydalanib turli ob-havo sharoitlarida olingan shahar tasvirlaridan PM 2.5 ni regressiya orqali bashoratlashni amalga oshirgan [12]. Ma va boshq. (2020) multimodal yondashuvni taklif etishgan bo‘lib, ular tasvirdan olingan belgilarni meteorologik ma’lumotlar bilan birlashtirish orqali bashorat aniqligini 12% ga oshirgan [13].

Metodlar

Mazkur tadqiqotda Hindiston va Nepalda olingan tasvirlar bazasi hamda ularga mos PM 2.5 ko‘rsatkichlariga ega bo‘lgan ma’lumotlar bazasidan foydalanildi. Olingan to‘plamda har bir tasvir fayl yoki CSV (Comma-Separated Values) — ma’lumotlarni jadval ko‘rinishida saqlashladigan fayl formatida ko‘rsatilgan bo‘lib, unda har bir tasvirni joriy ifloslanganlik darajasi berilgan. Tasvirlar bazasida umumiy 12240 ta 224x224 o‘lchamdagi tasvirlar mavjud bo‘lib, ularda ko‘proq osmonni ifloslanganligi e’tiborga olingan.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
Location	Filename	Year	Month	Day	Hour	AQI	PM2.5	PM10	O3	CO	SO2	NO2	AQI_Class	
1	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-9.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
2	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-8.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
3	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-7.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
4	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-6.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
5	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-5.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
6	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-4.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
7	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-3.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
8	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-2.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
9	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-18.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
10	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-17.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
11	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-16.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
12	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-15.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
13	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-14.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
14	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-13.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
15	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-12.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
16	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-11.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
17	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-10.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
18	Biratnagar, Nepal	BRI_Un_2023-02-02-12.00-1.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
19	Biratnagar, Nepal	BIR_UNH_VF_2023-02-02-12.00-3-9.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
20	Biratnagar, Nepal	BIR_UNH_VF_2023-02-02-12.00-3-8.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
21	Biratnagar, Nepal	BIR_UNH_VF_2023-02-02-12.00-3-77.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
22	Biratnagar, Nepal	BIR_UNH_VF_2023-02-02-12.00-3-76.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
23	Biratnagar, Nepal	BIR_UNH_VF_2023-02-02-12.00-3-75.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy
24	Biratnagar, Nepal	BIR_UNH_VF_2023-02-02-12.00-3-74.jpg	2023	2	2	12:00	158	70.08	100.82	58.89	0.49	4.4	1.04	d_Unhealthy

Rasm 1. PM 2.5 ko‘rsatkichlari bilan berilgan ma’lumotlar

Modelni ishlab chiqish ikki bosqichda amalga oshirilgan bo‘lib, birinchi bosqichda tasvirlardan belgilarni ajratish amalga oshirilgan. Bunda EfficientV2B0 arxitekturasi qo‘llanilgan [14]. Mazkur model ImageNet bazasida oldindan o‘qitilgan bo‘lib, u tasvirlardagi eng muhim vizual belgilarni samarali ajratish imkoniga egadir [15]. Model chiqishida har bir tasvir uchun 1280 o‘lchamli vektor shakllantiriladi [16] va u havo sifatini vizual ifodasini raqamli fazoda aks ettiradi [17]. Modelni o‘qitishda xotiradan samarali foydalanish uchun 3000 ta namuna olingan. Bu belgilarni ajratish jarayonidagi xotira cheklovi bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan xatoliklarni oldini oladi. Bundan tashqari, model ma’lumotni yaxshi o‘rganishi uchun namunalarni tasodifiy berish talab etiladi [18] va PM 2.5 qiymatlar normalizatsiyalanadi. Belgilar ajratilgandan so‘ng mos PM 2.5 qiymatlari bo‘yicha kombinatsiyalanadi. Bu o‘qitish jarayonidagi yo‘qotishlarni kamaytirib o‘rganish aniqligini oshiradi [19].

Rasm 2. Tasvir va unga mos PM 2.5 ko‘rsatkichi

Ikkinchi bosqichda shakllantirilgan belgilar vektorlari FNNga kiruvchi ma’lumot sifatida uzatiladi. FNN quyidagicha tuzilgan:

- 256 neyronli qatlam (ReLU faollashtirish funksiyasi)
- Dropout (0.3) – overfittingni kamaytirish uchun
- 128 neyronli qatlam (ReLU faollashtirish funksiyasi)
- So‘nggi qatlam – 1 neyron, chiziqli faollashtirish funksiyasi bilan (PM 2.5 qiymatini bashoratlaydi).

CNN + FNN Regressiya Arxitekturası

Rasm 3. Model arxitekturası

Model Mean Absolute Error (MAE) funksiyasiga asosida o'qitildi.

Natijalar

Ushbu tadqiqotda ishlab chiqilgan neyron tarmoq modeli yordamida tasvir asosida unga mos havo sifati PM 2.5 ko'rsatkichi bashoratlash amalga oshirildi. Modelga kiruvchi sifatida tasvirlar, chiquvchi sifatida esa PM 2.5 qiymatlari olindi. Ma'lumotlar [0,1] oraliqqa normallashtirilib, model 3000 ta tasodifiy namunalar asosida o'qitildi [20].

Rasm 4. Xatolik funksiyasi grafigi

Rasm 5. MAE grafigi

Model o‘qitish bosqichida Test MAE = 0.072 va Test MSE = 0.011 qiymatlariga erishdi. Ushbu ko‘rsatkichlar modelni normallashtirilgan birliklarda yuqori aniqlikda bashoratlayotganini bildiradi. PM 2.5 qiymatlarini asl birlikka qayta o‘tkazilgandan so‘ng ham kutilgan natija olindi. Vizual tahlil uchun test to‘plamdan 6 ta tasvir tanlab olindi. Har bir tasvir ostida haqiqiy va bashoratlangan PM 2.5 qiymatlari ko‘rsatilgan. Olingan natijalar modelni umumiy tendensiyalarni to‘g‘ri saqlayotganini ko‘rsatadi biroq, ayrim hollarda bashorat haqiqiy qiymatdan chetlanishini ko‘rsatadi. Shuningdek, model chiziqli regressiya tendensiyasini o‘rganishga moyil bo‘lib, u yuqori ifloslanish darajalarida nisbatan pastroq aniqlikni ko‘rsatdi [21].

Xulosa

Tadqiqot natijalari asosida tasvirdan PM 2.5 qiymatini baholash imkoniyati mavjudligi va bu yo‘nalish havo sifatini kontaktlarsiz (Remote Sensing) monitoring qilish uchun istiqbolli yondashuv ekanligini ta’kidlash mumkin. Taklif etilgan neyron modeli asosida havo vizual belgilaridan muhim xususiyatlarni muvaffaqiyatli ajratib olindi va ular yordamida PM 2.5 qiymat kutilgan darajada baholandi. Biroq, modelni asl birlikdagi natijalari ma’lumot hajmi va turli sharoitlarda olingan tasvirlar xilma-xilligida aniqlikka sezilarli darajada ta’sir ko‘rsatishi mumkinligini ko‘rsatdi. Kelgusida model aniqligini oshirish uchun quyidagilarni amalga oshirish zarur:

- katta va muvozanatli ma’lumotlar bazalaridan foydalanish;
- tasvirlarni yorug‘lik va rang diapazonlarini standartlashtirish;
- modelni ilg‘or arxitekturalar bilan integratsiyalash;
- qo‘shimcha meteorologik xususiyatlarni multimodal kirish sifatida qo‘shish tavsiya etiladi.

Umuman olganda, taklif etilgan yondashuv havo sifatini avtomatik aniqlashda zamonaviy neyron tarmoqlar samaradorligini namoyon etdi va kelgusida sun’iy yo‘ldosh yoki mobil sensor tizimlariga integratsiyalash imkoniyatlari mavjudligini ko‘rsatdi.

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